

Numerical analysis of two hip implant surfaces

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Abstract— The goal of this study was to use the numerical approach in order to analyze the shear stress values of the two simple modifications of the hip implant surface. Numerical approach consisted of the implementation of the finite element method (FEM) for the simulation of the bone-implant interaction and for the calculation of the shear stress values of the two modified surface topographies in the titanium alloys (Ti-6Al-4V) implants.

I. INTRODUCTION

Total Hip Replacement surgery is a surgery in which the damaged parts of the hip joint are replaced with artificial ones [1]. When an implant is inserted into the fractured bone, the direct functional connection between the inserted implant and a bone starts to happen. In order to improve the osseointegration, implant with a rough surface should be used [2,3]. The goal of the present study was to obtain shear stress values for the modified hip implant surfaces using the finite element method.

II. MATERIALS & METHODS

In order to carry out computational simulations of different implant surface modification with spherical geometries and its interaction with bone, the finite element models of implant and bone (cortical and cancellous) were created.

Three different materials were used for the finite element analysis. Titanium Alloy (Ti-6Al-4V) was used as the implant material. Material properties (Young's modulus and Poisson's ratio) were obtained from the literature [4,5]. The constraints applied were adapted from paper [3]. For the load, we have used the maximum force value on the hip joint during the gait cycle for the average weight of 70kg. The implant surface was in contact with the cancellous bone. In order to simulate micro motions that can occur between cancellous bone and implant, friction coefficient of 0.39 was defined [5].

III. RESULTS AND CONCLUSIONS

Fig. 1 presents the shear stress distribution for the model 1. Looking at the spheric modifications, the shear stress values were in the range from 0.0495 to 2.3MPa. Fig. 2 shows the shear stress distribution for the model 2. Analyzing the spheric modifications, the shear stress values were in the range from 0.0563 to 2MPa. As with the model 1, the highest shear stress value was located on the spheric modification closest to the area where the force was defined.

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Figure 1. Shear stress value distribution for model 1.

Figure 2. Shear stress value distribution for model 2.

Shear stresses at the implant-bone interface should be minimized in order to promote bone ingrowth [2]. Comparing the two models, based only on the maximum shear stress value, we can say that the model 2 would be a better choice.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme PANBioRA under grant agreement No. 760921-2. This article reflects only the author's view. The Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The research has also been carried out with the support of the Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development, Republic of Serbia with projects III41007 and OI174028.

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